

University of Portsmouth

University of Portsmouth, Faculty of Business and Law

Title:

MSc Risk, Crisis, and Resilience Management

Module:

M32007-2023/24-SMMAY - Dissertation

Subject:

“What about Us”?

Can the UK Police Force THRIVE risk model be extended to:

Non-emergency services during multi-agency events?

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Date:

2nd January 2025

Word Count

9996

2. Resources for readers who may need support –

- [Bedfordshire domestic & sexual abuse partnership](#)
- [DASH website](#)
- [National Domestic Violence Helpline](#) (Tel: 0808 2000 247)
- [Women's Aid](#) - The national charity working to end domestic abuse against women and children. This site gives access to publications and research papers.
- [Asian Women centre](#);
- [Bruises on Children - Core Information from the NSPCC](#)
- [Refuge Organisation](#);
- <https://mensadviceline.org.uk> Men's domestic abuse helpline

3. Declaration

DECLARATION	
Word Count:	9996
Signed statement of originality: This project is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Science. I, the undersigned declare that this project report is my own original work. Where I have taken ideas and or wording from another source, this is explicitly referenced in the text.	
Signed:	<i>Ian Smith</i>
Date:	17 th DECEMBER 2024
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4. Acknowledgements

The Author: Ian P. Smith has attained the National Examination Board for Occupational Safety and Health – NEBOSH National Diploma and acted as a Consultant for the Bedfordshire Police Force, where the THRIVE principle was identified. Having previously served for Eight years in the Royal Navy as a Weapons Engineering Mechanic (Ordinance) followed by Twenty-one years of service as an Operational Firefighter and Incident Commander within the Northamptonshire Fire and Rescue Service.

My wife and family for allowing me the time and space with unwavering support.

Bedfordshire Police Force – for their huge support and commitment to my research, providing all resources to conduct the Table-top exercise at Kempston Headquarters. The Bedfordshire MASH Participants giving their time to engage in the Table-top Exercises, providing important and insightful primary data. a few Individuals of note:

Chief Constable *Trevor Rodenhurst* KPM Bsc (Hons)

Chief Superintendent *David Boyle* BA Mst (Cantab)

Detective Chief Superintendent *Zara Brown* Mst (Canatab) CMgr MCFI

Superintendent *Alex House* BA(Hons) Adv.Dip(CTRM) *mention* (Ben Searle, Tanveer Hussain and Sylwia Kozuch respectively)

University of Portsmouth—My supervisor, Mrs Maria Marcos, whose guidance has been exacting and constructive to all previous lecturers throughout the Msc course. My WhatsApp cohort classmates, THANK YOU for being such a remote support network.

Practitioners: Your work is so so incredible Thankyou

Survivors: You are not alone.

5. Purpose

Practical implications– Having a common language- a common approach summary risk assessment process, allows for the Chairperson of any MASH or MARAC event to cross-examine all attendees, their data (which they can freely share) can be broken down to specific points each open for discussion and agreement allowing for closure of the meetings where all attendees can be sure that all data, priorities and actions are confidently understood more importantly can be refreshed immediately as information changes.

Keywords / Acronyms:

Domestic Abuse Stalking and Harassment and Honour Based Violence - DASH

Independent Domestic Violence Advisor - IDVA

Joint Emergency Services Interoperability Programme - JESIP

Joint Strategic Needs Assessment – JNSA

Multi-Agency Risk Assessment Conference - MARAC

Multi-agency Safeguarding Hubs -MASH

(Joint) National Decision-making Model – (J)NDM

Threat, Harm, Risk, Intelligence, Vulnerability, Engagement - THRIVE

Paper type: Research paper, proof of concept.

“What about us”?

Can the UK Police Force’s THRIVE risk model be extended to: Non-emergency services during multi-agency events?

6. Abstract

The Primary data collected from a Bedfordshire MASH group minus Police Officers; 76% of participants specifically stated THRIVE would provide better risk management. 100% of the theoretical application of THRIVE to safeguarding Cases was shown to be applied as a summary assessment tool.

This study examines the potential extension of the THRIVE risk model, currently used extensively within UK police forces, to non-emergency services involved in multi-agency events: Social Services, Probation Services, and Third-sector organisations. While UK emergency services operate in compliance with the *Civil Contingencies Act (2004)* and the *Joint Emergency Services Interoperability Programme (JESIP)*, there is no equivalent mandated risk management model for non-emergency agencies, prompting the question: Can THRIVE be adapted to improve risk management and interagency coordination in these sectors? Speaking with a Social Worker within child safeguarding, they raised the question I intend to answer: **What about us?**

Using a mixed-methods approach, this research gathers primary data from professional discussions with practitioners involved in Multi-Agency events, including Multi-agency safeguarding hubs -MASH and Multi-agency risk assessment conferences -MARAC, along with secondary data from academic sources and Serious Case Reviews. Findings suggest that **THRIVE could enhance** risk assessment clarity and decision-making for MARAC and MASH events by offering a shared framework that supports effective communication and collaboration.

This study has implications for national policy, proposing that a unified approach to risk assessment across agencies could lead to greater accountability, compliance with GDPR, and improved national security. Practically, it offers a pathway for MASH / MARAC meetings to integrate a common risk language, allowing for real-time updates and comprehensive information sharing. This research supports the potential for THRIVE to foster a safer community through consistent, collaborative risk management across emergency and non-emergency services.

Key Summary: The THRIVE model does offer a clear and structured approach to enhancing communication, risk prioritisation, and accountability in multi-agency safeguarding events, for example, MASH and MARAC. It is particularly beneficial in fostering a unified approach across diverse agencies.

When used appropriately, THRIVE can be a valuable tool for improving outcomes in safeguarding and risk management.

The expansion of THRIVE as both a summary risk assessment tool and a dynamic risk assessment tool offers significant potential for improving risk management across the sectors of Policing, Social Services, National Health Services and the Ministry of Justice. It offers a unified approach, bringing together various elements of existing *MASH and DASH* risk tools potentially extended to include the *Joint National Decision-Making Model used within JESIP and SARA*, while its dynamic nature allows for ongoing updates, ensuring that agencies can react swiftly to changing circumstances. THRIVE's versatility makes it a powerful tool for multi-agency collaboration and for enhancing the effectiveness of existing, more static risk assessments.

WHAT ABOUT US? – You could all adopt THRIVE

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Chapter One – What About Us?

The Potential Role of the UK Police THRIVE Model in Multi-Agency Risk Assessment

7.0 Introduction

7.1. Background and Context

Effective risk assessment and information sharing in multi-agency settings are critical for safeguarding vulnerable individuals in the United Kingdom. The increasing complexity of safeguarding and public protection has led to the rise of multi-agency approaches, including Multi-Agency Safeguarding Hubs – MASH and Multi-Agency Risk Assessment Conferences (MARAC). These functions were developed in response to high-profile cases that revealed systemic failures in communication and coordination across agencies responsible for protecting vulnerable individuals, culminating with legislative change in April 2001 of the *Criminal Justice and Court Services Act 2000*.

Despite these changes, numerous Serious Case Reviews (SCRs) and public inquiries have revealed systemic failures in risk management and data sharing, often with tragic consequences. The Serious Case Reviews (SCRs) of Peter Connelly (Baby P) (Laming, 2009), Victoria Climbié (Laming, 2003), and Fiona Pilkington (Walker et al., 2010) highlighted critical gaps in risk assessment, information sharing, and collaboration between law enforcement, social services, and healthcare professionals. These cases underscored the need for more effective, standardised tools to summarise risk swiftly and accurately across multiple contexts.

Multi-agencies aim to enhance coordination by facilitating structured discussions and shared decision-making among professionals. However, one ongoing issue is the need for a tool that provides a quick and comprehensive summary of risk, enabling practitioners to make informed decisions. The THRIVE model, originally designed as a triage framework for UK Police control rooms, has the potential solution to this problem.

7.2. Problem Statement

Despite the increasing use of the THRIVE model in law enforcement settings, there is limited research on its application in multi-agency frameworks within MARAC and MASH. These events require methods that assess immediate risks and facilitate coordinated action across

Multiple agencies in a dynamic, fast-moving Incident. Current risk assessment tools lack a standardised approach to summarising professional departmental assessments that is both comprehensive and adaptable to different types of high-risk cases, including domestic abuse, violent offenders, or vulnerable individuals. This research aims to address this gap by exploring whether the THRIVE model can serve as a viable summary risk assessment tool enhancing the coordination and efficiency of risk management in these complex cases.

7.3. Research Aims and Objectives

The purpose of this paper is to answer the primary and sub-set research question: Can the UK Police Force THRIVE risk model be extended to Non-emergency services during multi-agency events?

- A) What are the barriers to common risk data sharing?
- B) How can existing Risk methodologies be combined to provide a summary Risk Management Plan?
- C) Can THRIVE be applied to Multi-agency events, for example, MASH MARAC processes?
- D) Can THRIVE be used to create a safer community?

This research includes the research principles of formal and informal qualitative study grounded in interpretive epistemology, knowledge gained through secondary data analysis, expert consultation, and steps for bias reduction.

1. Interpretivist Epistemology: This approach values subjective meaning and context, aligning with perspectives that emphasise understanding over objective truths (Bell et al. 2019).
2. A qualitative blend of Secondary Data: The researcher engages in interpretive principles through analysis of datasets from other sources, fitting with an interpretive base.
3. Expert Consultation with Bias Reduction through Third-Party Assessment: Conducting a tabletop exercise with professionals provides a constructivist element, enabling hypothesis proof-of-concept through shared multi-agency expertise. To mitigate potential bias of the researcher, an independent third-party assessor is included, ensuring a more objective and balanced assessment of ideas (Bell et al. 2019).

Bias is a recognised concern in qualitative research, as researcher or participant expectations can influence findings (Roulston & Shelton, 2015).

Together, these methods reflect an epistemological commitment to viewing knowledge as interpretive, strategic, operational-focused, and context-dependent through case studies while incorporating steps to enhance the rigour and credibility of findings through bias reduction.

7.3.1 Narrative:

There is a lack of research outside of the United Kingdom Police Forces on the use of THRIVE as a Risk Management tool.

This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the THRIVE model as a summary risk assessment tool in multi-agency settings, specifically MASH and MARAC. The key objectives of the study are:

- To assess the applicability of THRIVE in summarising risks across diverse cases handled by MASH and MARAC leads.
- To explore the perceptions and experiences of professionals from different agencies using THRIVE in these multi-agency frameworks.
- To analyse the strengths and limitations of THRIVE in facilitating cross-agency communication and decision-making.
- To review secondary data from existing research of THRIVE, MARAC, and MASH events to contextualise findings and provide a comprehensive evaluation.
- Obtain primary data from a MASH group within Bedfordshire and analyse quantitative and qualitative data of practitioners.

7.4. Significance of the Study

Adopting THRIVE as a summary risk assessment tool could provide significant potential for improving the MASH and MARAC processes. This improvement could directly benefit policymakers by addressing key findings often highlighted in SCRs or Independent Police Complaints Commission – (IPCC). These reviews often identify gaps in risk management, multi-agency communication, and victim protection table 1:

Table of Serious Case Reviews (SCRs) and IPCC Findings (2002–2022)

Case Name	Year	Type	Key Findings on Multi-Agency Risk Assessment	Reference
Baby P (Peter Connelly)	2007	SCR	Systemic failures in risk assessment and coordination among agencies; lack of shared information about ongoing abuse.	Laming, H. (2009). <i>The Protection of Children in England: A Progress Report</i> . HM Government.
Victoria Climbié	2000 (follow-ups into the 2000s)	SCR	Deficiencies in risk assessment across social services, health, and police; poor collaboration despite clear warning signs.	Laming, H. (2003). <i>The Victoria Climbié Inquiry Report</i> . HMSO.
Finley Boden	2020	SCR	Significant shortcomings in risk assessment when returning a child to an unsafe environment; inadequate planning and monitoring.	Local Safeguarding Children Board (2022). <i>Serious Case Review: Finley Boden</i> .
Daniel Pelka	2012	SCR	Poor multi-agency information sharing; individual concerns identified but not connected to assess overall risk.	Coventry Local Safeguarding Children Board (2013). <i>Serious Case Review Re: Daniel Pelka</i> .
Ian Tomlinson	2009	IPCC	Lack of coordinated risk assessments during G20 protests; insufficient input from medical advisors and external agencies.	Independent Police Complaints Commission. (2010). <i>Investigation Report: Ian Tomlinson</i> .
Sean Rigg	2008	IPCC	Inadequate collaboration between mental health services and police; poor risk assessment before escalation.	Independent Police Complaints Commission. (2012). <i>Investigation Report: Sean Rigg</i> .
Fiona Pilkington and Francesca Hardwick	2007	IPCC	Failures by police and councils in risk assessment despite repeated reports of harassment; poor communication between agencies.	Independent Police Complaints Commission. (2009). <i>Investigation Report: Pilkington and Hardwick</i> .

TABLE 1: RISK MANAGEMENT FAILURES

Wider Policy Benefits: By adopting THRIVE in this context, UK policymakers could enhance greater accountability of how agencies assess and manage risk, addressing key issues raised in SCRs. The benefits extend to individual practitioners by reducing sole reliance on their interpretation of another’s risk perception. The Domestic Abuse Stalking and Harassment - DASH process currently used is an excellent framework for initial data gathering, the use of THRIVE could close the Risk loop by providing summary oversight.

For policymakers, using THRIVE may help meet the SCR recommendations by providing greater structured summary risk assessment that reduces the likelihood of missed warning signs. This could inform national policies regarding mandatory risk evaluation processes and protocols across agencies, creating consistency in the identification of threats across the UK. Streamlined National Standards: THRIVE could be incorporated into national guidelines, creating a unified risk assessment model for all agencies. Reducing regional disparities in how cases are handled and ensuring that lessons from SCRs are applied consistently across the UK.

7.5. Structure of the Dissertation

This dissertation is structured as follows:

Chapter 1 Background to existing methodology and multi-agency groups.

Chapter 2 reviews existing literature on the THRIVE model and its applications in law enforcement and multi-agency contexts.

Chapter 3 outlines the research methodology, including the mixed-methods approach and the use of secondary data.

Chapter 4 presents the results of the TTE, drawing from both qualitative and quantitative data analysis.

Chapter 5 discusses the Conclusion

Chapter 6 recommendations for future research and policy implications.

Chapter Two – Literature Review

8.0 Literature Review

The following sections will review academic research, including barriers to multi-agency collaboration, including data sharing and cultural differences between agencies. It will also Reference the high-profile SCRs of The following cases: Fiona Pilkington, Victoria Climbié, and Peter Connelly (Baby P), respectively, to illustrate how the THRIVE model could serve as a framework for more structured risk assessment, understanding, transparency, interrogative and data sharing process.

The depth of the research applied to this literature review of Multi-agency Risk Assessment is not intended to reflect a full literature review of all available data or academic research, the field of Multi-agency Risk Assessment is extensive and complex in its application, to allow focus on the aim of this dissertation, to test this hypothesis that the THRIVE model could be transformational in the way such events produce risk management strategies, the literature review is an investigative type to identify existing evidence that focuses upon the principles and failings of Multi-agency risk management principles.

Accessing research from different search platforms, **Google Scholar, Google, University of Portsmouth online library.**

MARAC and MASH frameworks rely heavily on multi-agency cooperation and effective information sharing to assess and manage risks, particularly in cases of domestic violence (MARAC). Robinson R (2004) evaluated the Cardiff MARAC, highlighting how risk assessment through multi-agency collaboration can reduce recidivism in domestic abuse cases by fostering a shared understanding of risks between agencies, verifying that no single agency holds all the information necessary to assess risks fully, making collaboration essential (Robinson, 2004) UK Home Office (2011) focused on the consistency of agency attendance at MARAC meetings and the challenges faced by agencies in balancing workload and resources to participate effectively in risk assessment (Home Office, 2011).

8.1 What is a MARAC?

As described by *Central Bedfordshire Child Services* (Appendix 1) Multi-Agency Risk Assessment Conference is a monthly meeting where various agencies discuss the risk of harm for People experiencing domestic abuse and make safety plans to enable a risk management plan. The aim is to reduce the risk of them becoming repeat victims.

The meetings with partner agencies, for example, Bedfordshire Police, Social Services, Probation Services, Health managers, Voluntary Sector charities and Housing providers are made aware of high-risk cases of domestic abuse.

MARAC Assessment: See Appendix 4

- MARAC is a multi-agency response mechanism designed to manage high-risk cases of domestic abuse.
- It is not a risk assessment tool but rather a risk management process. In a MARAC, different agencies meet to share information about the victim and create a coordinated action plan to increase their safety.
- The MARAC process follows from a high-risk DASH assessment or other indications of risk.
- DASH: A risk identification tool that is used to determine if a victim is at high risk.
- MARAC: A multi-agency case management process for addressing the needs and safety of victims assessed as high risk, often following a DASH assessment.

8.2 What is a DASH assessment?

The DASH see Appendix 2 risk assessment model was developed as a risk assessment tool to identify and respond to high-risk cases of domestic violence and related forms of abuse, including honour-based abuse and forced marriage.

Designed to improve processes on how agencies assess and manage domestic abuse in the UK. The case of Maria Stubbings (Independent Police Complaints Commission. 2013) highlighted the failure of existing systems to adequately assess and manage the risk.

The DASH risk assessment Richards L (2009) aimed to be a standardised risk identification tool that could be used consistently across the UK by various frontline professionals, including the police, social workers, healthcare providers, and domestic abuse advocates.

DASH Tool consists of 27 questions (Appendix 2) the assessor can evaluate the level of risk (standard, medium, or high) and determine what steps need to be taken to protect the victim, including referrals to specialised services or a MARAC for high-risk cases.

8.3 What is MASH?

A Multi-Agency Safeguarding Hub (MASH) is a collaborative framework endorsed by Munro E (2011) and the Care Act (2014), bringing together professionals from multiple organisations to ensure the safety and well-being of vulnerable individuals, particularly children and at-risk adults.

Key Features:

1. Collaboration: MASH includes representatives from agencies like social services, the police, health services, education, and housing working together in one location.
2. Information Sharing: Partners share relevant information securely and efficiently to build a comprehensive understanding of risk and needs.
3. Risk Assessment: The shared insights help assess risk levels and prioritise cases for appropriate intervention.
4. Action Coordination: Agencies coordinate responses to safeguard individuals and provide the necessary support.

8.4 Integration with Multi-Agency Approach

The DASH risk assessment model was developed alongside the increasing use of MARACs, which had been introduced in the early 2000s as the primary tool used to determine whether a victim should be referred to a MARAC meeting. The MARAC process relies on the DASH assessments to identify cases that need urgent multi-agency intervention.

The DASH tool remains a cornerstone of domestic abuse risk assessment in the UK and is used by various agencies to ensure victims receive timely and appropriate intervention.

DASH is a risk assessment methodology, whilst MASH and MARAC are both risk management processes used in the context of domestic violence and abuse cases, serving different purposes, and are used at different stages of intervention.

The HM Government document Home Office (2011) delivered a strategic review of missing adults and children where it is stated (p5) that a key provision will be the need for local agencies to deliver bespoke risk-based response in such cases continuing late to reaffirm as part of the responsibilities and role (p23) that local authorities in joint working with the Police to ensure local protocols are in place agreeing a multi-agency approach to managing risk. This strategic review fails in its approach to providing a practical risk framework for all the agencies to be able to summarise complex risk data as could be provided by the shared.

Use of THRIVE. It does reference the development of a Joint Strategic Needs Assessment – JNSA however, this is designed to focus on the Health and wellbeing commissioning services.

8.5 Barriers to Multi-Agency Data Sharing

One example of a MARAC (Appendix 3) from Bedfordshire involved 17 agencies, all of which must have Individuals who are registered to attend the MARAC and have their log-in details to gain access to the data-sharing platform – *Modus* is hosted at a secure data centre in the UK. If that individual is unable to attend a MARAC session, any deputies sent are unable to gain access to existing information or enable the sharing of updated information. Each agency represented must have its own GDPR policy, which may differ from each other agency, creating a barrier to access or sharing of data. A 23-page Data-sharing Impact Assessment is required to be completed for each case, during this process, any of the agencies involved may place an objection to this assessment, delaying the completion, which leads to a delay in creating the MARAC for the Victim.

This Research has consistently identified data sharing as one of the most significant challenges in multi-agency safeguarding. One prominent barrier is the lack of a shared framework for assessing and communicating risk. According to Hood et al. (2016), professionals from different sectors often operate within siloed systems;

“In the findings, there was evidence that once the boundary to child protection has been crossed, there was a tendency even for experienced practitioners to retreat into mono-professional siloes in the face of any ensuing difficulties”.

Munro (2011) highlights that confidentiality concerns and data protection regulations, the *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*, can further complicate data sharing between agencies. Professionals may be hesitant to share information for fear of breaching confidentiality, even when sharing it could prevent harm.

The lack of a common language or standardised approach to risk assessment compounds these challenges as identified during the TTE Primary data -see appendix 6, White, Hall, & Peckover (2009) identified solutions to this silo working with the introduction of a ‘common language’ introducing procedures to standardise assessment frameworks, it is evident that the introduction of DASH and similar joint working protocols go some way to allow for commonality, an area where there remains a gap is the introduction of a common language summary Risk Assessment where the hypothesis that THRIVE could be that framework.

In their recent 2024 article, Monaghan Waring.S and Giles.S (2024) conducted research relating to managing multi-agency working during missing children incidents. Of the source data they reported from, 19 highlighted that poor information sharing is a key barrier to multi-agency management, continuing to qualify that many agencies hold back important information or share such information is not reported in a consistent or consolidated format. A key obstacle identified included a fear of breaching Data Protection legislation. Concluding that most literature referenced stated the need for multi-agency collaboration to be more effective, with the need for greater and open sharing of data. Of the seven – vii recommendations (p18), recommendation (v), “*shared understanding of terminology,*” does not provide any solutions of how to provide a method of achieving this recommendation, in addition, the conclusions push for the need for future research to focus on solution-orientated outcomes. It is argued that by using THRIVE in this scenario and all multi-agency events, recommendation (v) can be achieved along with overcoming the barrier to data sharing without breaching data protection legislation, as THRIVE could be used as a summary of confidential or sensitive data, not the disclosure of it.

8.6 Cultural differences

Differences of opinions and ways of long-standing working between agencies present another significant barrier to effective multi-agency collaboration. Darlington et al. (2014) stated that agencies, including the police, social services, and health professionals, often have different organisational priorities, working methods, and understandings of risk, which can lead to conflict and confusion when attempting to collaborate on safeguarding cases. Reeves C (2012) referenced an observation study conducted between February 2004 and March 2005, which involved twelve separate MARAC events, included in the conclusion that due to the hierarchal function of a MARAC -Police take primacy, occasionally resulting in tensions between the attending agencies, extending further stating:

“ ...relationships engendered by traditional and cultural roles as well as organisational hierarchies may sometimes be counter-productive...” highlighting the study for further work to be conducted on the consequences of risk assessment and risk management.

Differences in focus can result in conflicting assessments of risk, as seen in that of Peter Connelly and Victoria Climbie, where law enforcement and social services failed to

Coordinate effectively. Fitzgerald J (2019) further suggests that these differences in professional cultures often lead to a lack of trust between agencies, which can discourage open communication and data sharing. Reeves E (2012) concluded following extensive research of the function of MARAC concluded, tensions existed for two main reasons

- 1) poor information transference, which left some agencies working with incomplete information, which led to
- 2) agencies were less engaged in the process. This conclusion may lead to risk factors being un-disclosed or given a lesser engagement priority. Reeves continued to conclude that further study was required around poor risk management consequences and a better strategy to overcome cultural and hierarchal positions.

Kettle and O'Reilly (2020) explore the issue of role ambiguity, noting that professionals are often unclear about their responsibilities in multi-agency settings this was borne out from the primary data where Participants noted the lack of ownership was a barrier to practitioner decision-making. Cultural differences in decision-making processes and risk thresholds can result in delayed or inadequate responses to vulnerable individuals, as was the case with Fiona Pilkington.

Chapter Three – Research

9.0 Research Methodology

The chosen research methods—a tabletop exercise (TTE) coupled with quantitative and qualitative questionnaires including purposive sampling, reflective feedback, Likert-scale questionnaires, and secondary data research—are particularly suited for exploring multi-agency safeguarding practices. Compared to other methods outlined by Bell, Bryman, and Harley (2019), this mixed-method approach offers specific advantages by enabling a broad spectrum of research complexity, interactivity, and theoretical underpinnings of safeguarding processes.

9.1. Suitability for Exploring Complex Social Processes

The TTE, as an immersive and participatory method, provided a dynamic platform for understanding how professionals from multi-agencies collaborate, communicate, and make decisions in safeguarding scenarios. This aligns with Bell, Bryman, and Harley's (2019) argument that qualitative methods are particularly effective in capturing context-dependent human interactions. Unlike surveys or secondary data analysis alone, the TTE enabled direct observation of real-time decision-making and inter-agency collaboration.

9.2. Integration of Secondary Data.

Supported primary data, secondary data was used to identify and compare risk assessment methods. Academic literature and sector references on safeguarding practices were reviewed to understand the theoretical and practical implications of different frameworks, including analyses of the THRIVE framework and its structured, multi-dimensional approach to risk assessment (College of Policing, 2017). Studies by Bowers et al. (2019) and Munro (2011) were particularly insightful, highlighting the importance of standardising risk assessment to minimise ambiguity in safeguarding decisions.

9.3 Applicability of Grounded Theory to the Research Methodology

Grounded theory (GT), a qualitative research methodology developed by Glaser and Strauss (1967), was particularly applicable to this research study. Grounded theory is designed to develop theories and hypotheses that emerge directly from gathered and analysed data. Focussing on inductive reasoning and iterative analysis makes it an ideal principle for

exploring the complex nature and the need for a collaborative process demanded in safeguarding practices, as demonstrated in the study.

9.4 Purposive Sampling for Expertise Representation

Purposive sampling was employed to ensure the inclusion of participants with professional expertise in safeguarding, consistent with Palinkas et al. (2015) guidance on qualitative research. Representatives from the Bedfordshire MASH, Central Bedfordshire Council, and Luton Town Council were selected in collaboration with Bedfordshire Police to reflect the field roles applicable in safeguarding. This approach ensured that the exercise captured a representative cross-section of perspectives. Alternative sampling strategies, for example, random sampling, would have been inappropriate for this research, as they risk including participants lacking the specialised knowledge required for meaningful contributions. The snowballing sampling method was determined to be too time-restrictive for the time of this research, along with the lack of resources to filter the participant sampling group although this method has the potential to create a greater number of participants, it was deemed inappropriate at this stage.

9.5 Emphasis on Contextual Seriousness

The inclusion of high-profile case studies—Peter "Baby P" Connelly, added contextual seriousness to the study. These cases, analysed through Serious Case Reviews (SCRs) and Independent Office for Police Conduct (IOPCC) reports, served as critical tools for framing. By presenting the exercise with this case, the study drew on secondary data to contextualise the practical application of risk assessment frameworks.

9.6 Use of Mixed Methods for Comprehensive Insights

A Likert-scale and Open qualitative questionnaire followed the TTE, providing a quantitative provision to the qualitative research. This approach reflects Creswell and Plano Clark's (2017) emphasis on mixed-methods research for achieving both depth and breadth in data collection. In addition, open feedback discussions provided reflective, participant-led insights, while observational notes allow for the capture of specific verbal statements, by nature, are subjective to the participants and should carry significance as a personal view only and not that of the sector the participant represents.

9.7 Comparison to Alternative Methods

While surveys and interviews provide breadth, they are less effective for capturing the dynamic, interactive processes central to safeguarding. They would also possibly fail to replicate the contextual challenges of safeguarding scenarios.

- **Secondary Data Alone:** While secondary data offers valuable theoretical insights, relying solely on it would not have allowed for the observation of current practices or the interaction between professionals during decision-making. The combination of secondary data with the TTE enriched the research by providing both theoretical and practical perspectives.
- **Experiments:** Experimental methods, while useful for hypothesis testing, are rigid and less suited for exploring the social dynamics of human interaction and the context-dependent nature of safeguarding practices.

9.8 Ethical and Reflexive Considerations

Throughout the study, ethical principles were upheld, including informed consent, the right to withdraw, and reflexivity, consistent with the University of Portsmouth's ethical guidelines. The integration of open feedback sessions and observational notes further reflects Tracy's (2010) emphasis on participant voices and researcher reflexivity in qualitative research. By combining primary data collection through the TTE with secondary data research on risk assessment frameworks, the study achieved a comprehensive and contextually grounded exploration of safeguarding practices. Compared to alternative methods described by Bell, Bryman, and Harley (2019), this approach effectively balanced theoretical rigour with practical insights, capturing the complexity and interactivity of multi-agency collaboration.

9.9 Research Design

The research methodology can be described as a qualitative, epistemological method that emphasises understanding the social processes and interactions within multi-agency safeguarding practices. This method aligns with a constructivist epistemology, knowledge is constructed through interaction and shared understanding (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). By employing a table-top exercise (TTE) as the primary method of data collection, the study sought to explore how professionals from different agencies collaboratively assess and respond to complex safeguarding scenarios.

A mixed-methods research design was used to explore whether the THRIVE model could improve multi-agency risk assessment and data sharing. This approach included both qualitative and quantitative methods.

1. Literature Review: A review of existing research on multi-agency collaboration, barriers to data sharing, and serious case reviews, including that of Fiona Pilkington and Peter (Baby P). Connelly and Victoria Climbié.
2. Quantitative Questionnaire: to gather insights into practitioners' experiences with current risk assessment models and their views on the potential benefits of using THRIVE in multi-agency contexts.
3. Case Study Analysis: analysis of Serious Case Reviews and public enquiries to identify how THRIVE could have addressed the issues of communication and risk management
4. Research Analysis: Thematic Analysis, supported by Constant Comparative Analysis, is the most effective method for this study as it provides for comparing differing types of risk processes.. It ensures a systematic yet flexible approach to analysing qualitative data, enabling the study to generate meaningful, actionable insights into the use of risk assessment frameworks like THRIVE in multi-agency environments.

10.0 Initial proof of concept 2016 – Bedfordshire Police Primary Data.

A qualitative field study was conducted by the researcher on the potential for THRIVE to be expanded beyond the use of the Police control room operators to the wider Policing departments.

This study had the support of senior Police Officers, with the then *Superintendent David Boyle, Head of Local Policing*, acting as professional lead and research reviewer a formal THRIVE project board was assembled consisting of Seven Police Officers of Sergeant Rank and above respectively from seven different remits of responsibility plus the author of this paper.

Five professional Interviews were conducted with Serving Police Officers. Explaining this was a voluntary, informal research interview, the participants were free to withdraw consent at any time, and this process was a proof-of-concept research, the results of which would not at this stage create a shift in existing Risk Management policy. All interviewees consented to discuss their views, raising balanced arguments about barriers to implementation.

The results of these Interviews overall received a positive response. Including.

- *“the department needs to improve the Risk process – THIRVE may be that vehicle”*
EC
- *“Can be used with working partners – Social Services, Probation Service” – EC*
- *“enable a structured approach to Dynamic Risk Assessment’ – GM*
- *“provide a better tool for supervisory managers in decision making” - GM*
- *“lack of interdepartmental communication – All departments need to be aware of THIRVE” – EC*
- *“the ability to add information on a single framework to pass on to others” – GM*
- *“supportive to front-line Officers” – KE*

Barriers to the principle and implementation of THIRVE responses included:

- *“ how to change traditional ways of working?” – GM*
- *“when will there be time for training for this?” - KE*
- *“accountability – Fear – Staff may feel that THIRVE may be used to hold them to additional account!” – EC*
- *“how would this work when working with other Police Forces?” – GM*

This initial research provided sufficient positive responses to conclude that THIRVE **did have the potential** to be implemented to a wider audience than the 999- control room triage, which would require further testing.

11.0 – Research TTE discussion with Bedfordshire Police Force

Following the University of Portsmouth’s ethical approval, an approach was made to a senior Police Officer of Bedfordshire Police *Chief Superintendent David BOYLE*, - CS BOYLE professionally known to the researcher – sec10.0.

CS BOYLE requested a professional telephone discussion with the researcher to ensure the Ethics profile and Research Aim fit within the core values of Bedfordshire Police Force.

CS BOYLE introduced me to *Detective Chief Superintendent Zara BROWN* – DCS BROWN, also employed by Bedfordshire Police Force, *Head of Public Protection and Crime Command*. DCS BROWN’s team engage with multi-agencies for the Prevention and Investigation of Child Safeguarding, Violence Against Women and Girls, Domestic Abuse,

Stalking Harassment and Honour Based Violence. DCS BROWN introduced the researcher to her Management Team, intending to support the research where possible. *Superintendent Alex HOUSE – Supt HOUSE* became the lead planner supported by his support staff and colleagues.

11.1 Pilot event

Bhattacharjee A (2012) p23 discusses the importance of conducting a pilot test before the data collection event, in recognition of this principle, a Pilot briefing and test process was conducted two days before the TTE. This was held at Bedfordshire Police Headquarters using a separate group of individuals those not involved in the TTE. The purpose was to test the timelines of the TTE along with the physical testing of resources and I.T. The Pilot event highlighted that the quantitative questionnaire was potentially biased toward Police processes, which participants not from the Police may provide limited or nil response, the questions were reviewed to ensure this bias was eliminated. Discussions took place regarding the role-play of participants and who would be declared to act as Chair for the TTE?

Historically and in normal MASH management, the senior police officer would act as a Chair, the discussion focussed on the benefit of using a different agency participant to act as chair as this TTE could act as a catalyst for change in not only the Risk Assessment and Decision-Making process but as a wider implication that if a non-police officer was Chair would that change how the MASH conducted its process and potentially change bias?

It was agreed by the researcher that this was digressing from the key aim of the TTE suggesting such a change for another event.

It was noted that the question was raised at all about the change of Chair from the Police, raising some professional curious questions;

1. Was there an existing unconscious bias already in this type of event?
2. Was there confirmation bias inherent?– would it be easier to agree with a Police Officer than to challenge?
3. Was this a sign of a barrier to decision-making?
4. Was this a symptom of differing Risk Assessment approaches not providing clarity or consistency?

11.2 Participants and Sampling

Participant profiles were described to the Senior Police Officer *Superintendent, Mr Alex House*, acting as liaison and host of the TTE. The profile was:

1. A person who has attended a multi-agency event, in this instance, a MASH event:
2. Ideally, Participants should be from diverse agencies to allow for a broader spectrum of input.
3. A person who has authority from their respective employer to attend and provide input which can be used as primary data
4. Ideally, a volunteer who is keen to participate

Participants were identified and invited by *Superintendent Alex House*, supported by his team of serving Police Officers and administration staff.

The TTE simulated real-world safeguarding scenarios, incorporating case studies of high-profile incidents. These cases were selected due to their profound impact on safeguarding policies and practices, with findings drawn from Serious Case Reviews (SCRs) and reports from the Independent for Police Conduct (IPCC).

The TTE was structured to enable as broad qualitative data as possible within the timescale available during the Scenario event. To achieve this, the Participants were randomly divided into four groups the caveat of the groups was that Groups must have a mix of agency participants. Two groups participated in the morning sessions and two in the afternoon.

Half of the groups utilised the THRIVE model; the other groups employed their respective departmental risk analyses to examine the case studies. Each group engaged in assessing the risks and vulnerabilities presented in the cases before reconvening to present their findings to an impartial Chair, a Police Officer, to mitigate potential researcher bias (Tracy, 2010). One group explicitly applied the THRIVE framework in their summary, enabling a comparative analysis of the methodologies.

Following the group presentations, participants completed a Likert-scale questionnaire Appendix 6 to capture their perceptions of the exercise and the risk assessment methodologies. The exercise concluded with an open feedback discussion chaired by Bedfordshire Police, allowing participants to engage in reflective dialogue.

Observational notes taken by the researcher provided additional qualitative data, capturing non-verbal cues and group dynamics. The researcher concluded the sessions by reminding participants of their right to withdraw their consent, aligning with ethical standards set by the *University of Portsmouth*.

By incorporating high-profile case studies, the research emphasised the importance of historical context and the evolution of safeguarding practices, aligning with academic theories of experiential learning and collaborative inquiry (Kolb, 1984; Schön, 1983). A purposive sample of 16 participants was recruited, comprising practitioners from each of the professional groups. The purpose of the sample was to ensure equal representation of Social Workers and Child Protection practitioners. A range of professions were selected for this study as they are key professional groupings involved in multi-agency [child safeguarding] events. This hypothesis aimed to explore the application of THRIVE to not only meet a strategic need but could be taught to and delivered by Field Practitioners. All of these practitioners had current or previous experience engaging with multi-agency events, in this case, MASH.

All participants gave written informed consent to participate in the research. Appendix 5

12.0 Hypothesised Examples.

THRIVE could be a useful tool for multi-departments within Bedfordshire Police and multi-agencies outside of Bedfordshire Police; these agencies are now referred to as MARAC and MASH. To evaluate the hypothesis, worked examples demonstrate the use of THRIVE, applied to the case studies, these examples show the adoption of THRIVE for use as a summary assessment tool. If the THRIVE model had been used, could it have provided a structured approach addressing the key recommendations from these reviews and enabled clearer decision-making?

12.1 Peter Connelly (Baby P)

Peter Connelly's death in 2007 highlighted profound failures in communication and risk recognition. Lord Laming fundamentally criticised the disjointed responses from various agencies, including social services, healthcare providers, and police the SCR recommended clearer processes for identifying and responding to escalating risk.

How THRIVE Could Address SCR Recommendations ?:

- **Threat & Harm:** The SCR emphasised the missed signs of abuse and poor attention to the visible injuries Baby P sustained. The **THRIVE model** would have required a focus on identifying immediate threats to Peter's safety through a unified assessment of harm.

- **Risk:** The SCR recommended better risk prioritisation and dynamic assessment. THRIVE's risk-focused approach would push agencies to actively monitor the level of danger and respond promptly to changes in Peter's condition and environment.
- **Vulnerability:** The SCR pointed out that Peter's vulnerability as a young child was not adequately considered. THRIVE would give central importance to this vulnerability, ensuring that Peter's inability to articulate his suffering was considered.
- **Engagement:** The SCR recommended improved communication across agencies. THRIVE would enhance MARAC by fostering better multi-agency engagement, ensuring that health, social care, and police share critical information in real-time.

Incorporating the THRIVE model could have addressed these systemic failures by creating clearer risk assessments and ensuring that Peter Connelly's case may have been prioritised based on his vulnerability and the ongoing threat of harm.

12.2 Victoria Climbié

This case revealed systemic failure across child protection services. The SCR highlighted a lack of coordination, failure to act on clear signs of abuse, and insufficient focus on the escalating risks to Victoria's life.

How THRIVE Could Address SCR Recommendations:

- **Threat & Harm:** The SCR called for earlier recognition of the signs of abuse and emphasised that agencies failed to understand the level of threat to Victoria. THRIVE would have required an immediate assessment of harm based on her injuries, pushing agencies to act urgently.
- **Risk:** The SCR recommended a more dynamic approach to risk assessment. THRIVE would focus on the holistic risk of Victoria's case involving escalating danger.
- **Vulnerability:** as a young child from a different cultural background. THRIVE would emphasise the importance. Prompting professionals to view her as particularly vulnerable due to her isolation, language barriers, and dependency on her abusers – extended family.
- **Investigation:** The SCR recommended more thorough investigations into children's living conditions and familial circumstances. THRIVE would have been an emphasis on probing deeper into Victoria's home life and applying a more forensic lens.

- **Engagement:** The SCR recommended the need for multi-agencies to link up sooner where indicators dictate. THRIVE would make a specific highlight for the Engagement element to be addressed.

12.3 Fiona Pilkington

The SCR (Barker, I. 2010). criticised police and local authorities for failing to recognise the cumulative risks of ongoing harassment and the vulnerability of Fiona and her daughter.

How THRIVE Could Address SCR Recommendations:

- **Threat & Harm:** The SCR highlighted that authorities did not assess the persistent harassment as a significant threat. THRIVE would have required a focused assessment of the harm caused by the ongoing anti-social behaviour, flagging a serious and escalating Threat.
- **Risk:** THRIVE would emphasise dynamic risk assessment, ensuring that repeated incidents were seen as part of a broader pattern of harm rather than isolated events.
- **Vulnerability:** The SCR stressed that Fiona’s mental health struggles and her daughter’s disabilities were not considered. THRIVE would give priority to these vulnerabilities, pushing agencies to take proactive measures to protect the family.
- **Engagement:** The SCR pointed to a lack of engagement between police, mental health services, and local authorities. Under THRIVE, improved multi-agency engagement would ensure a coordinated approach to stop the harassment and provide ongoing support to the family.

The use of the THRIVE in this case could have highlighted the growing risks faced by Fiona and her daughter, compelling MARAC to intervene sooner and provide the necessary support.

13.0 Doesn’t DASH provide a summary common approach?

The DASH risk model is for assessing the risk of domestic violence, primarily focusing on identifying high-risk cases through a structured checklist of questions. While DASH provides valuable insights into specific risk factors for domestic abuse, it is limited in its ability to function as a comprehensive, summary risk assessment tool across diverse multi-agency environments. (Robinson, 2017).

One of the critical limitations of DASH is that it focuses heavily on victim reports and the context of domestic violence, potentially excluding other risk factors of vulnerability, mental health issues, or broader public safety concerns that might be relevant in multi-agency cases. As a result, it does not fully address the need for a holistic, dynamic summary of risk across different domains of harm (Stanley & Humphreys, 2014).

The THRIVE model can provide a broader, more flexible summary risk assessment across multiple contexts. This flexibility is crucial for multi-agency events, which handle a wider range of cases, including violent offenders and high-risk individuals in the community (College of Policing, 2019). The THRIVE model's structure allows for a comprehensive assessment that not only captures immediate risks but also considers long-term vulnerabilities and the potential for harm across different agencies.

THRIVE allows for any MASH/ MARAC practitioner to focus on a specific area(s) of the assessment for clarity of understanding, thus maintaining an updated, accountable, holistic understanding of the case (Boulton & Cole, 2020). DASH can contribute to silos of communication, where each agency might interpret the risk differently based on their specific focus, leading to fragmented responses.

The THRIVE model promotes a shared language and understanding across agencies, helping to prevent communication breakdowns and ensuring that all professionals involved are aligned in their assessment and actions (Ransley et al., 2017). This can reduce the margin of error in risk management and help avoid blame being placed on individual practitioners due to misunderstandings or miscommunications.

DASH is a valuable tool for assessing domestic violence risks, its narrow focus and static nature limit its effectiveness as a summary risk assessment tool in multi-agency contexts.

14.0 Data Collection and Analysis

(Bell, Bryman, and Harley 2019) The table-top exercise (TTE) is designed to simulate a real-world scenario and evaluate the application of the THRIVE model in multi-agency safeguarding [MASH] context. The data analysis methods applied for this type of qualitative and participatory research involve thematic analysis by comparative analysis to explore patterns, insights, and differences in participant responses and group interactions.

14.1 Thematic Analysis

A systematic approach to identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within qualitative data gathered during the TTE. Themes centred around the principles of data-sharing, training, and improvement.

Methodology:

A Review of the observation notes and feedback from participants was conducted to gain an holistic understanding, including patterns that may have emerged depending on the professional agency the individuals were representing.

14.2 Comparative Analysis

Used to compare the effectiveness of THRIVE against participants' views of the current process of risk assessment tools during the TTE.

Methodology:

The TTE provided Four groups of Participants, which allowed for Group Comparison.

This method was chosen as best suited to deliver contextual insights **into** the perception of Hazards and Risk depending upon the professional agency. This method was also chosen as it facilitated a method to enable the examination of the structured approach of THRIVE influences group-think and decision-making outcomes.

Key Metrics compared being two control groups not using THRIVE compared to two groups using THRIVE as a summary risk assessment.

- The professional subjective view of participants on the Quality of risk summaries.
- Clarity in communication by use of common language
- Efficiency in summarising and identifying threats and vulnerabilities.

14.3 Coding

Four groups were created, and a unique code was assigned to each participant, this allowed for the anonymity of the individual, the principle being this would allow for comments from a personal and professional viewpoint without fear of consequence. Coding participants by Professional Agencies was also included to allow for the comparative analysis between agencies. However, there was due consideration that, given the limited number of Participants from each agency, by doing such coding, an individual may be identified.

To overcome this, Participants were provided with a separate method of indicating their views via an anonymous method of the Post-it note wall – no results obtained by this. The groups were decided by the attending Police Officer whose only guidance from the researcher was to mix the Professional skill set and the mix the same department participants in the best way achievable. This gave the following four coded groups.

CODE	PARTICIPANT RANGE
A	1-4
B	1-5
C	1-3
D	1-3

TABLE 2: GROUP CODING

14.4 Likert-Scale and Quantitative Analysis

To complement qualitative data, the TTE event included the use and analysis of the Likert-scale questionnaire data. See Appendix 6

Methodology:

1. Review the scores for each question and identify trends in perceptions.
2. Use descriptive statistics (e.g., averages, standard deviations) to summarise results.
3. Correlate quantitative findings with qualitative themes to cross-check

This combination ensures a robust, multi-approach evaluation of the TTE outcomes, aligning with the dissertation’s mixed-method approach and objectives.

Chapter Four – Results and Analysis

15.0 Results analysis of quantitative data – Likert appendix 6

The scores from each Coded group were recorded, and an average score was obtained, the High and Low scores have been highlighted for analysis. The four coded groups produced a range of scores see Table :

Section A – Question CODE	Section A- CODE	Section A- CODE	Section A- CODE
A	B	C	D
Low = 8	Low = 8	Low = 2	Low = 2
High = 9	High = 9	High = 6	High = 10
Section C – Question CODE			
A	B	C	D
Low = 20	Low = 20	Low = 20	Low = 20
High = 21	High = 16	High = 21 & 15	High = 21

TABLE3 : SUMMARY OF LOW AND HIGH RATING DENOTED BY QUESTION NUMBER OF LIKERT.

15.1 Rating of results:

Question 20

Question 20 received the lowest agreement score. This suggests that the use of THRIVE does not represent a significant barrier to its adoption within the existing process. Furthermore, it indicates that practitioners strongly agree THRIVE as an enhancement tool.

Question 21

Seventy-five per cent of coded groups rated Q21 highest among all statements. Coded group B rated Question 16 the highest; however, Question 21 was their second most agreed statement with an average score of 4.25 compared to 4.4. Given this small margin, this finding supports the argument that participants strongly agreed the potential hindrance posed by training implications could be mitigated by the benefits of adopting the system.

Questions 8 and 2

Questions 8 and 2 each accounted for 50% of the overall score. These results are significant because both questions pertained to data sharing, which was a central theme of four questions in Section A. This finding suggests that data sharing is an area of concern among practitioners.

Question 9

Question 9 achieved 50% agreement among coded groups A and B. Groups C (6) and D (10) also demonstrated alignment, though both ranked Question 9 in second place. This result highlights that collaborative working is regarded as a significant improvement over operating within agency silos.

LIKERT QUESTIONS SECTION A CURRENT POSITION OF DATA SHARING – GROUP CODE A	SCORE A1-A2-A3-A4 Score/4 = Average
1	2 2 4. 4 = 3
2	3 3 3. 3 = 3
3	4 3 4. 3 = 3.5
4	4 3 2. 4 = 3.25
5	2 4 4. 2 = 3
6	4 4 4. 5 = 4.25
7	2 3 4. 4 = 3.25
8 *	2 2 2. 2 = 2
9 **	5 5 5. 5 = 5
10	3 4 5. 4 = 4
11	3 3 2. 2 = 2.5

LIKERT QUESTIONS SECTION C THE USE OF THRIVE – GROUP CODE A	SCORE A1-A2-A3-A4
15	3 4 5. 4 = 4
16	4 3 5. 4 = 4
17	3 4 4. 4 = 3.75
18	1 3 3. 2 = 2.25
19	2 2 5. 2 = 2.75
20 ***	2 4 1. 3 = 2.5
21 ****	4 4 5. 4 = 4.25

***Question 8:**

Training provided for Risk Management and Data-sharing practices is adequate?

****Question 9:**

Collaborative working in MASH and similar settings significantly improves outcomes for vulnerable persons

***** Question 20**

THRIVE would be more of a hinderance than a help?

****** Question 21**

As a practitioner, with additional training I would be confident in using THRIVE

TABLE 4: GROUP A RESULTS

LIKERT QUESTIONS SECTION A <i>CURRENT POSITION OF DATA SHARING –</i> GROUP CODE B	SCORE B1-B2-B3-B4- B5 Score/4 = Average
1	2 4 4 2 5 = 3
2	2 4 3 3 4 = 3
3	5 4 3. 2 4 = 3.5
4	2 2 3. 1 4 = 3.25
5	4 4 4. 5 3 = 3
6	3 4 5. 4 3 = 4.25
7	5 2 2. 4 4 = 3.25
8 *	5 3 2. 3 4 = 2
9 **	5 4 5. 5 4 = 5
10	5 4 4 5 5 = 4
11	3 2 2 3 4 = 2.5

LIKERT QUESTIONS SECTION C <i>THE USE OF THRIVE –</i> GROUP CODE B	SCORE B1-B2-B3-B4-(B5 partly complete)
15	5 5 4 3 x = 4.25
16***	5 3 5 4 5 = 4.4
17	5 4 3. 4 4 = 4
18	5 4 3 1 4 = 3.4
19	5 2 3 3 4 = 3.4
20****	1 3 3 2 2 = 2.2
21	5 4 4 4 x = 4.25

***Question 8:**

Training provided for Risk Management and Data-sharing practices is adequate?

****Question 9:**

Collaborative working in MASH and similar settings significantly improves outcomes for vulnerable persons?

***** Question 16**

The use of THRIVE as a summary assessment would enhance inter-agency understanding?

******Question 20**

THRIVE would be more of a hinderance than a help?

TABLE 5: GROUP B RESULTS

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LIKERT QUESTIONS SECTION A CURRENT POSITION OF DATA SHARING – GROUP CODE C	SCORE C1-C2-C3 Score/4 = Average
1	3 2 1 = 2
2*	2 1 1 = 1.33
3	3 2 2 = 2.33
4	3 1 1 = 1.66
5	4 5 1 = 3.33
6**	5 5 4 = 4.66
7	4 3 x = 3.5
8	4 2 3 = 3
9	5 4 4 = 4.33
10	5 5 1 = 3.66
11	4 2 2 = 2.66

LIKERT QUESTIONS SECTION C THE USE OF THRIVE – GROUP CODE C	SCORE C1-C2- (C3 partly complete)
15 ***	5 5 x = 5
16	5 5 4 = 4.66
17	5 5 4 = 4.66
18	5 5 4 = 4.66
19	5 5 3 = 4.33
20****	1 1 2 = 1.33
21*****	5 5 x = 5

***Question 2:**

Training provided for Risk Management and Data-sharing practices is adequate?

****Question 6:**

I have, on occasions, mis-understood terminology of other agencies?

***** Question 15**

How likely do you think the use of THRIVE could provide better risk assessment summaries in multi-agency settings?

******Question 20**

THRIVE would be more of a hinderance than a help?

******* Question 21**

As a Practitioner, with a little training I would be confident in using THRIVE?

TABLE 6: GROUP C RESULTS

LIKERT QUESTIONS SECTION A <i>CURRENT POSITION OF DATA SHARING –</i> GROUP CODE D	SCORE D1-D2-D3 (partly scored) Score/4 = Average
1	3 3 1 = 2.33
2*	2 1 1 = 1.33
3	3 4 2 = 3
4	3 2 1 = 2
5	4 1 1 = 2
6	4 3 4 = 3.66
7	2 5 x = 3.5
8	2 3 3 = 2.66
9	3 5 3 = 3.66
10**	4 5 5 = 4.66
11	2 4 2 = 2.66

LIKERT QUESTIONS SECTION C <i>THE USE OF THRIVE –</i> GROUP CODE D	SCORE D1-D2- C3 (partly scored)
15	4 5 4 = 4.33
16	4 5 4 = 4.33
17	4 5 3 = 4
18	4 5 3 = 4
19	4 5 4 = 4.33
20***	4 1 2 = 2.33
21*****	4 5 x = 5

***Question 2:**

Training provided for Risk Management and Data-sharing practices is adequate?

****Question 10:**

Resource constraints (eg staffing, technology) negatively impact the effectiveness of the Risk Management process?

***** Question 15**

How likely do you think the use of THRIVE could provide better risk assessment summaries in multi-agency settings?

******Question 20**

THRIVE would be more of a hinderance than a help?

******* Question 21**

As a Practitioner, with a little training I would be confident in using THRIVE?

TABLE 7: GROUP D RESULTS

16.0 Qualitative question results

To aid the analysis of the quantitative data, a mixed method approach was used to enable professional opinion to be captured through an Open questionnaire link found in Appendix 6 the results from each coded group enable a comparative analysis to indicate common trends for both benefits and barriers for THRIVE in this case within the MASH forum.

QUESTION	PARTICIPANT A1-A2-A3-A4
11. what are the most common barriers you face when sharing risk-related data across agencies?	A1) concerns around consent and data sharing. A2) agencies not wanting to own info sharing responsibilities. A3) gaining consent is big issue, when this is needed and when not. A4) parental consent, delays with info sharing.
12. how do you think these barriers affect the overall effectiveness of multi-agency risk management?	A1) impacts, information sharing A2) <u>less</u> effective outcomes for children, delay in safeguarding. A3) delay in service users having access to support, mis-understandings as to what action to take if no consent given. A4) missed opportunities to assure young people are safeguarded.
13. describe an example where ineffective data -sharing negatively impacted a risk assessment	A1) gaps in data on adults living at an address where an adult was classed as a danger to children. A2) lack of information sharing from health appointments fabricated illness. A3) delays in agencies providing checks, timescales in MASH are not in line with other agencies. A4) details of family members not provided missed opportunities to discuss concerns.
14., what improvement would you suggest to enhance multi-agency risk assessment practices?	A1) professionals to record the impact of the risk assessment on the clients welfare A2) more opportunities to meet other agencies in person to discuss risk progress. A3) I think a generic risk assessment could improve risk assessment. A4)

TABLE 8: GROUP A RESULTS – SECTION B

QUESTION	PARTICIPANT A1-A2-A3-A4
<p>22. how could thrive improve the current risk assessment process in multi-agency settings?</p>	<p>A1) it would standardise a format for information sharing. update professionals with information. A2) could be incorporated into tri-borough referrals. A3) better analysis of risk, a more thoughtful approach for service users. A4) risk would be more apparent</p>
<p>23. what barriers would you consider to introducing thrive into multi-agency settings?</p>	<p>A1) Issues surrounding [client] consent. A2) consent is required to record and share on every occasion in MASH except for immediate risk. A3) service user consent, how updates are shared. A4) consent, increase of workload, difficult to incorporate in the short-term.</p>

TABLE 9: GROUP A RESULTS – SECTION D

QUESTION	PARTICIPANT B1-B2-B3-B4-B5
11. what are the most common barriers you face when sharing risk-related data across agencies?	<p>B1) sharing accurate information, consent prevents sharing, partner agencies mis-interpret terminology, different risk thresholds and risk perception.</p> <p>B2) consent, fear, time constraints.</p> <p>B3) Consent, no shared I.T, no shared language, political disclosure.</p> <p>B4) being able to contact correct people in a timely manner.</p> <p>B5) information not timely available to MASH guidelines.</p>
12. how do you think these barriers affect the overall effectiveness of multi-agency risk management?	<p>B1) Lack of information providing inaccurate data.</p> <p>B2) delay in sharing</p> <p>B3) not always timely pertinent information, not always clear understanding.</p> <p>B4) delays in making risk decisions in good time which could lead to things being missed.</p> <p>B5) delays outcomes and decision making, should be swift essential for safeguarding.</p>
13. describe an example where ineffective data -sharing negatively impacted a risk assessment	<p>B1) <i>UNABLE to interpret</i></p> <p>B2) not receiving timely information to make a risk decision.</p> <p>B3) child safeguarding; didn't check with all agencies involved, child remained at risk for 6 months immediately removed due to risk.</p> <p>B4) crucial information delayed meant case closed however in hindsight needed more information.</p> <p>B5) not having enough family background information can impact risk assessment.</p>
14., what improvement would you suggest to enhance multi-agency risk assessment practices?	<p>B1) incorporated into social care referrals, THRIVE used by all agencies, Common threshold of risk.</p> <p>B2) better working relationships to gain confidence.</p> <p>B3) everyone being asked to make a risk assessment, method to quantitatively measure risk, shared language and understanding.</p> <p>B4) everyone having a shared understanding of thresholds.</p> <p>B5) more staff</p>

TABLE 10: GROUP B RESULTS – SECTION B

QUESTION	PARTICIPANT B1-B2-B3-B4-B5
22. how could thrive improve the current risk assessment process in multi-agency settings?	B1) all agencies using a common language, better inter-agency working, better outcomes. B2) better quality referrals, fluid risk. B3) shared language, ask referrals to make a risk assessment. B4) it allows greater analysis of risk. B5) it would give structure to risk assessment.
23. what barriers would you consider to introducing thrive into multi-agency settings?	B1) I see no barriers. B2) consent. B3) practitioners would send a THRIVE assessment instead of a referral form. B4) Consent for sharing information, may not work for closed cases. B5) consent, more case loading, not fitting to timescales.

TABLE 11: GROUP B RESULTS – SECTION D

QUESTION	PARTICIPANT C1-C2-C3
11. what are the most common barriers you face when sharing risk-related data across agencies?	C1) receiving feedback in a timely manner, schools too slow in sending data. C2) consent. C3) consent, timescales
12. how do you think these barriers affect the overall effectiveness of multi-agency risk management?	C1) impacts the decision. C2) we are unable to effectively risk assess due to this barrier causing significant delays in decision making. C3) reduce the holistic picture if consent is not given for a child / family assessment.
13. describe an example where ineffective data -sharing negatively impacted a risk assessment	C1) school took 3 days to share information and did not realise the importance. C2) School provided basic “voice of child” like the three houses tool doesn’t allow for whole risk of a child. C3) <i>No comment</i>
14., what improvement would you suggest to enhance multi-agency risk assessment practices?	C1) to all use the same risk assessment tool for example THRIVE. C2) a system that allows data sharing on a need-to-know basis so we don’t have to wait. C3) easier to locate information data-base

TABLE 12: GROUP C RESULTS – SECTION B

QUESTION	PARTICIPANT C1-C2-C3
22. how could thrive improve the current risk assessment process in multi-agency settings?	C1) all practitioners working with the same process. C2) <i>No Comment</i> C3) enable better sharing of information
23. what barriers would you consider to introducing thrive into multi-agency settings?	C1) none C2) <i>No Comment</i> C3) none

TABLE 13: GROUP C RESULTS – SECTION D

QUESTION	PARTICIPANT D1-D2-D3
11. what are the most common barriers you face when sharing risk-related data across agencies?	D1) consent, different protocols create delay in info sharing. D2) consent; the threshold to over-ride consent is too high, agencies not willing to share crucial info due to privacy law-GDPR. D3) consent, time constraints, family engagement.
12. how do you think these barriers affect the overall effectiveness of multi-agency risk management?	D1) timescales impact decision making and assessments. D2) delay and inaccurate decisions, not informed of all the risks. D3) severely impact outcomes, putting children at risk.
13. describe an example where ineffective data -sharing negatively impacted a risk assessment	D1) information can't cover all areas delays in health and education information. D2) family presented at Hospital delay in obtaining information from local authority meant child sent home. D3) <i>No comment</i>
14., what improvement would you suggest to enhance multi-agency risk assessment practices?	D1) clearer process on a national level including IT data systems. D2) one data-base allowing visibility on statutory information across all agencies, live updating and flagging. D3) better way for version control, ability to quickly access timelines, platform sharing.

TABLE 14: GROUP D RESULTS – SECTION B

QUESTION	PARTICIPANT D1-D2-D3- D4
22. how could thrive improve the current risk assessment process in multi-agency settings?	D1) one concise way regardless of threshold and profession. D2) live agency sharing crucial. D3) <i>No Comment</i>
23. what barriers would you consider to introducing thrive into multi-agency settings?	D1) people trying to personalise it to suit when the idea is same for all. D2) None D3) <i>No Comment</i>

TABLE 15: GROUP D RESULTS – SECTION D

16.1 Analysis of qualitative data.

Of the questions answered, a common theme for **Section B** revolved around the issues of lack of information and Consent, 73% of participants identified CONSENT to be the most common barrier to sharing, whilst 53.3% stated that timescales led to delay in decision-making with notable reference suggesting that the lack of appreciation of need between agencies was not fully appreciated. Other standout individual comments came from B2, who indicated there was a fear factor of sharing information through a lack of understanding of the thresholds of sharing data this was also linked to D2 stating privacy law prevented individuals from sharing, D2 also stating the over-riding threshold to bypass consent in cases of child protection was too high (children’s commissioner 2024) to allow timely accurate, holistic risk decisions, Q13 examples occasionally indicated this has caused real-time concerns.

A2 highlighted the issue of ownership of responsibility, indicating this to be a cultural issue, *further research would be needed* to investigate the inner cultures of departments concerning data ownership. During the TTE observation, the area of consent was discussed, it was stated that Parental Consent (except for emergency intervention) was the biggest barrier, confirmed by the results. Further discussion highlighted the frustration of the participants where they have shown professional curiosity regarding a child, for example, inappropriate behaviour, welfare or language deficit, but are unable to speak to the child alone without the consent of the parent, who may indeed be suspected by the practitioner be the cause of neglect.

Not having this consent and with no determinate risk assessment that would score the child at high risk, the practitioner is tied in their options and actions of sharing their concerns outside that of their respective line manager (Children’s Commissioner 2024).

Q14 created a mix of responses drawing no outstanding trend; however, it can be argued that the need for a national data-access IT system may be beneficial although the costs of such a system would be considerable, it does show there is a need for geographic transfer or access to vulnerable persons, suggesting a THRIVE summary assessment could be more accessible than confidential or sensitive protected data being open source.

Section D is focused on the THRIVE model Q22; participants gave strong examples of how THRIVE could improve the Risk Assessment process. **76% of all groups gave strong acknowledgement that THRIVE would provide better data-sharing / Risk Assessment, whilst 46% clearly stated the use of a common language as a key benefit, these two statistics could not give a clear definition if 76% participants included “common language” as part of their thinking when describing “better”?**

Q23 - **It is clear that 54% of Participants saw the issue of [parental] Consent** as the single barrier to implementing THRIVE. It was discussed during the Open discussion of the TTE that THRIVE might be exempt from GDPR / Consent as the information given by practitioners may be able to be redacted given THRIVE is a summary assessment of official risk doctrine. **31% stated No Barriers to implementation**

17.0 Discussion and Implications.

The findings from this research may have significant implications for improving multi-agency collaboration. The THRIVE model could offer a standardised approach to risk assessment addressing the barriers identified in the literature, including inconsistent risk thresholds and cultural differences between agencies. By providing a common language for discussing risk, THRIVE could facilitate better communication and data sharing, which has been a recurring problem. Children’s Commissioner (2014) released a statement on the murder of Sara Sharif where, once again, it was highlighted that lessons must be learnt on how data-sharing amongst agencies must be improved.

The implementation of the THRIVE model has transformative potential for both clarity of risk assessment and multi-agency collaboration. It addresses systemic issues of inconsistent methodologies, poor communication, and siloed working, creating a method for a unified, dynamic, and victim-focused approach.

However, achieving these benefits will depend on the successful adaptation of THRIVE to non-policing contexts, adequate training, and ongoing evaluation to refine its application across diverse multi-agency scenarios.

17.1 Cultural Adaptation and GDPR

Although the THRIVE can be adapted to suit the needs of all sectors involved in safeguarding, section 10 of the Children Act 2004 places a duty on key MASH stakeholders to cooperate and improve the well-being of children and young people.

This includes the *proportionate sharing of information*, where appropriate, to make the best decisions for children and young people at risk. To achieve this, stakeholders can sign an *Information Sharing Agreement* specifying what data can be shared and what happens to that data. Managerial safeguards ensure that sensitive information is only accessed by those who ‘need to know’ about it, in the case of Emergency referral, the practitioner making the call can be reticent to divulge too much sensitive information, and on occasions, practitioners may give incomplete details due to the lack of understanding of the GDPR agreement or the lack of assurance that the person they are reporting to is on the “need to know” list, this, in turn, may lead to the risk assessment being skewed due to lack of complete information.

It is argued in this dissertation that the use of THRIVE allows for the practitioner to summarise their assessment without fear of accidental breach of GDPR. Further research is needed to pilot the model in multi-agency settings and assess its effectiveness in real-world applications.

Chapter Five – Conclusions

18.0 Conclusions

This dissertation has explored whether the THRIVE model could improve risk assessment and data sharing in multi-agency events. Through a review of serious case reviews, academic literature, and professional interviews, it is evident that THRIVE has the potential to address many of the systemic failures seen in high-profile cases, including those of Fiona Pilkington, Peter Connelly, and Victoria Climbié. However, implementation challenges remain, particularly in terms of cultural adaptation and training. Future research should focus on piloting the model in multi-agency settings to assess its long-term impact on safeguarding outcomes.

THRIVE is suited to allow for dynamic risk assessment, originally designed for policing purposes to assess the urgency and type of response required for calls and incidents, demonstrating how this is currently applied daily as a dynamic assessment.

18.1. THRIVE as a Summary Risk Assessment Tool Across Sectors

The THRIVE model's core components align well with the principles used in various risk assessment methodologies. Its application as a cross-sector tool can streamline the assessment process by focusing on the following:

Threat: THRIVE emphasises identifying immediate and potential threats. This principle remains central to risk assessment processes extending to OASys (Her Majesty's Prison and Probation Service, 2002) in the justice sector or MASH in social services. Incorporating this component allows agencies to assess immediate threat(s) (HM Home Office, 2014) to individuals or communities, whether from offenders or within vulnerable households.

Harm: THRIVE includes an evaluation of the possible harm to individuals, which could apply to victims of domestic abuse and children at risk.

Risk: THRIVE's risk component offers a simplified but broad evaluation of potential risk factors. This aligns with specialised assessments that include the Risk Identification Checklist for domestic abuse or DoLS (Department of Health and Social Care (2008)

Investigation: primarily police-focused, this component can be reinterpreted for other sectors. In social services, the "investigation" could refer to the thorough assessment of a child's situation, while in the justice system, it might refer to the investigation of the risk.

posed by offenders using assessment tools RM2000 (Thornton, D., & Knight, R. 2003) or Static-99 (Hanson, R. K., & Thornton, D. 2000)

Vulnerability: The emphasis on vulnerability across THRIVE aligns well with risk assessment methods CAF (Department for Education and Skills. (2006) or ACCT (Her Majesty's Prison and Probation Service. (2007)). . By expanding THRIVE, agencies can quickly identify vulnerable individuals in various contexts, from domestic abuse victims to children and adults at risk.

Engagement: Engagement assesses the need for an ongoing response, communication, or intervention, similar to MARAC or Prevent frameworks that rely on multi-agency collaboration. THRIVE's engagement element supports decisions around multi-agency interventions and ongoing safeguarding, making it versatile for cross-sector risk management. By expanding THRIVE, all these elements can be adapted into a summary tool that would serve as a common language across agencies. This could foster better coordination, eliminate redundancy in risk assessments, and provide a more unified approach to managing threats, harm, and vulnerability across all sectors. Enhancing Risk Prioritisation and Decision-Making.

18.2 Disadvantages of Using THRIVE in Multi-Agency Events

The open discussion highlighted the disadvantages of using THRIVE, which would require further discussion by policymakers before introducing THRIVE as a policy change. Training in the use of THRIVE has been identified as a disadvantage however, with clear planning, training is a key element of any change management.

18..2.1 Potential for Oversimplification

While THRIVE provides a clear framework, there is a risk of reducing complex and nuanced cases into overly rigid categories, which might miss subtle dynamics.

Example: In MARAC, the emotional and psychological impact of coercive control may not be fully captured if too much focus is placed on immediate physical threats. Governance structures are required to ensure practitioners do not misuse THRIVE because it is perceived easier to complete than the respective Risk Assessment needed

18.2.2 Increased Administrative Burden

The systematic nature of THRIVE may require additional time and resources, which can be problematic in high-volume, high-pressure environments.

Example: In MASH, staff managing hundreds of referrals may struggle to apply THRIVE in some cases.

During the TTE, there was an element introduced by the researcher to instruct participants from cohorts B and C, this consisted of a PowerPoint presentation -Appendix 8 and use of case study application. It was found that with short, precise instruction, the participants responded that they could easily introduce THRIVE with little administrative burden.

18.2.3 Dependence on Training and Consistency

Successful implementation of THRIVE relies on training and consistent use across agencies.

Without this, the model may lead to inconsistent assessments and outcomes. Example: If police and social services apply THRIVE differently in MASH, it could lead to conflicting priorities, undermining the collaborative process. It was identified that providing the THRIVE framework was understood, this greatly enhanced the communication between participants, opening conversations which may have previously not happened.

An example of this was during the TTE scenario, one participant identified Threats from the case study of Peter (Baby P) Connelly coming from his mother however, there were other persons living in the property, including a 15yr girlfriend of the brother of the partner of Peter's mother, whilst the participant was summarising the case another participant immediately noted in the "I" – Intelligence? Who is this 15-year-old girl? Who is the brother? Are there separate safeguarding concerns outside that of Peter Connelly, this professional was allowed to formally record into THRIVE and discussed by all, creating an "E" – Engagement action which, had this been a live case, would have prompted an action to monitor the situation of the 15yr girl. It was argued that this could be a distraction from the actual work of monitoring the primary case (Peter Connelly) and that the case social worker may be outside their respective consent boundary. However, the ability to use THRIVE did allow for recognition of the potential risk to the 15yr old crucially, without breaching that consent or boundary, it created an informal piece of risk Intelligence that could be allocated to others as appropriate.

18.3. THRIVE as a Dynamic Risk Assessment Tool

THRIVE is inherently a **dynamic risk assessment tool**, meaning it continuously adapts to the evolving nature of threats and risks based on real-time information. This makes it ideal for assessing situations where risks fluctuate rapidly, and its adaptability can also be extended across other sectors, including social services and the justice system. Situations can change for example a small Fire at an at-risk property, the attending Fire Service and/or Police Officers may apply their professional assessment and deem the fire to be small and insignificant, making cursory reporting notes for general statistics or Insurance company claims, however by the 999 operators being able to state that this is an at-risk property a THRIVE assessment could be created “I” – Intelligence [a small fire] this update although having little impact for the attending services MAY have major impact to other agencies if they are alerted. Using THRIVE dynamically could trigger a risk rating increase, which, in turn, MAY create an “E”- Engagement change by a case social worker. There may have been verbal “T”- Threats of arson made to the “V”- Vulnerable person, which in this example are now realised.

18.3.1 Supporting Multi-Agency Collaboration

THRIVE's ability to track and reassess risk dynamically makes it particularly suited for multi-agency working. As agencies work together to manage cases (e.g., high-risk offenders or vulnerable children), THRIVE's dynamic model allows for continuous updates, ensuring that risk management strategies evolve in line with the latest information.

18.3.2 Tailored Interventions

As new concerns about neglect or abuse can be quickly incorporated into a THRIVE assessment, prompting changes to intervention strategies before harm escalates, Davies et al. (2023) discussed in their article on the complexity of implementing multi-agency risk assessments citing Barlow and Walklate (2021) that perhaps the best assessor could arguably be the victim-survivor adding more complexity and subjectivity to the Risk Assessments fundamentals of attempting to rate the level of Risk. In reply to this statement, the THRIVE model could be used by the victim-survivor, allowing for immediate capture of how a serious situation has developed over time or is foreseeably escalating over an immediate timescale. Could a victim-survivor provide a more holistic view of their situation, which could assist practitioners in understanding the nuances of their risk and provide more tailored support?

19.0 General Benefits of THRIVE Based on SCR Recommendations

Holistic Risk Assessment: The Serious Case Reviews repeatedly called for a more integrated approach to assessing risk. THRIVE’s structure ensures that agencies collectively consider threat, harm, and vulnerability, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the situation at hand.

Proactive Risk Management: SCRs recommended a dynamic and proactive approach to risk. The THRIVE model requires continuous risk reassessment and prioritisation, ensuring that high-risk cases receive immediate attention within MARAC.

Clearer Communication and Engagement: SCRs consistently identified poor communication as a key failure. THRIVE mandates better engagement between agencies, ensuring information is shared and coordinated interventions are planned.

Prioritising Vulnerability: One of the critical gaps in these cases was the failure to adequately consider the most vulnerable individuals, whether children or people with disabilities. THRIVE’s focus on vulnerability ensures that such factors are central to MARAC discussions and intervention strategies.

The three case studies used where the THRIVE model was applied could have provided a structured, collaborative risk assessment process. The key recommendations from the Serious Case Reviews call for precisely the kind of proactive, holistic, and multi-agency approach that THRIVE offers.

Chapter 6 – Recommendations and further research

20.0 Recommendations

Following the research conducted, including the primary data from Bedfordshire MASH group, the following is proposed.

Recommendation	Benefit
1. Create a working party of a representative from each Multi-agency to agree THRIVE terminology and context	Develop common language and break down inter-agency barriers
2. Allow an observer to apply the principles of THRIVE during multi-agency live cases to help develop the culture change.	Develop the application principle to any multi-agency event – Including 999 responders
3. Agree between all agencies the boundaries of the use of THRIVE for example: used a summary or an immediate referral tool NOT a replacement to national or departmental risk assessment procedures	Agree joint agency application and maintaining existing due process
4. Ensure THRIVE assessments are GDPR compatible and where they may not be given the context of its respective use.	Ensure legal boundaries are known to prevent practitioners being fearful of disciplinary or breach of confidentiality
5. Introduce regional agencies and medical trusts to the THRIVE principles to enable broader data and risk sharing capabilities	Creates a broader geographical understanding which, could close the gap of vulnerable people being represented to different Hospitals or Local authorities.
6. Develop a governance structure to enable the oversight of the correct use of THRIVE including a body able to co-ordinate multi agency risk assessments with the joint agency approach of being able to extract data from cases to overlay a THRIVE	Enables corporate and individual accountability rigour. Allow for a formal review and auditing process. Provides for professional curiosity to be recorded and assessed by senior management potentially outside of the specific agency the professional is from, this could provide for political, financial or professional bias to be eliminated.

TABLE 16: RECOMMENDATIONS 1-6

7. Engage 3 rd Sector charities in the use of THRIVE within MARAC events including the additional training module for IDVA course	Gain the professional opinions from charities including Safelives.org Developing the IDVA course enables understating on a national basis for all individuals practicing within the UK
8. Develop the THRIVE protocols within JESIP	This would ensure 999 responders are conversant with THRIVE if working outside of a 999 only response event.
9. Develop the THRIVE+ programme with preventative agencies.	Widening the preventative programme to other agencies will deliver on the Police Force’s crime prevention and Every Life Matters goals.
10. Develop workshop events with multi-agencies to create consistency in approach and highlight deficiencies and good practice.	This will develop the professional interpersonal relationship between practitioners. Most benefit will be gained if a mix of management hierarchy attend these events.
11. Develop the use of THRIVE within the Justice system particularly for prisoner release summaries. MAPPA	This would allow for parole boards to share a summary assessment where specific or confidential data is not for general release. Sarah’s Law as an example or DASH
12. Provide a professional feedback process for effectiveness of THRIVE	Ability to assess the benefit and drawbacks of THRIVE in this wider context ensures the best time and resources are providing the intended outcomes of -Better.

TABLE 17: RECOMMENDATIONS 7-12

21.0 Further research

For THRIVE to be adopted within National Policy, further field trials would need to be conducted over a range of multi-agency events. This dissertation is primarily aimed at the MASH and MARAC events however, it was highlighted from the primary data inter-departmental professional culture can be seen as a barrier. Further fieldwork outside of these sectors may identify benefits from a single common summary Risk Framework, which could be applied to ALL operational risks.

Suggested field studies:

- Armed Policing
- Counter Terrorism
- Human Trafficking
- Violence Against Women and Girls
- Child Exploitation
- European Inter-Pol Intelligence

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Appendix 1 Central Bedfordshire Child Care Definitions

https://centralbedfordshirechildcare.proceduresonline.com/p_marac.html

- **Respect** - Charity providing resources for working with perpetrators of domestic abuse which will be of use to social workers and others undertaking work with this group.
- **The Freedom Programme** - a 12-week programme providing information about domestic violence to men and women.
- **The Hideout** - the first national website to support children and young people living with domestic violence, or to those who may want to help a friend. The site informs children and young people about domestic violence and helps them identify whether it is happening in their home.

Appendix 2 DASH checklist and Questions Web Link

DASH Checklist and Questions

<https://safelives.org.uk/resources-library/dash-risk-checklist/>

Ending domestic abuse

SafeLives Dash risk checklist Quick start guidance

You may be looking at this checklist because you are working in a professional capacity with a victim of domestic abuse. These notes are to help you understand the significance of the questions on the checklist. Domestic abuse can take many forms but it is usually perpetrated by men towards women in an intimate relationship such as boyfriend/girlfriend, husband/wife. This checklist can also be used for lesbian, gay, bisexual relationships and for situations of 'honour'-based violence or family violence. Domestic abuse can include physical, emotional, mental, sexual or financial abuse as well as stalking and harassment. They might be experiencing one or all types of abuse; each situation is unique. It is the combination of behaviours that can be so intimidating. It can occur both during a relationship or after it has ended.

The purpose of the Dash risk checklist is to give a consistent and simple tool for practitioners who work with adult victims of domestic abuse in order to help them identify those who are at high risk of harm and whose cases should be referred to a Marac meeting in order to manage their risk. If you are concerned about risk to a child or children, you should make a referral to ensure that a full assessment of their safety and welfare is made.

The Dash risk checklist should be introduced to the victim within the framework of your agency's:

- Confidentiality policy
- Information sharing policy and protocols
- Marac referral policies and protocols

Before you begin to ask the questions in the Dash risk checklist:

- Establish how much time the victim has to talk to you: is it safe to talk now? What are safe contact details?
- Establish the whereabouts of the perpetrator and children
- Explain why you are asking these questions and how it relates to the Marac

While you are asking the questions in the Dash risk checklist:

- Identify early on who the victim is frightened of – ex-partner/partner/family member
- Use gender neutral terms such as partner/ex-partner. By creating a safe, accessible environment LGBT victims accessing the service will feel able to disclose both domestic abuse and their sexual orientation or gender identity.

Revealing the results of the Dash risk checklist to the victim

Telling someone that they are at high risk of serious harm or homicide may be frightening and overwhelming for them to hear. It is important that you state what your concerns are by using the answers they gave to you and your professional judgement. It is then important that you follow your area's protocols when referring to Marac and Children's Services. Equally, identifying that someone is not currently high risk needs to be managed carefully to ensure that the person doesn't feel that their situation is being minimised and that they don't feel embarrassed about asking for help. Explain that these factors are linked to homicide and serious harm and that if s/he experiences any of them in future, that they should get back in touch with your service or with the emergency services on 999 in an immediate crisis.

Please pay particular attention to a practitioner's professional judgement in all cases. The results from a checklist are not a definitive assessment of risk. They should provide you with a structure to inform your judgement and act as prompts to further questioning, analysis and risk management whether via a

Appendix 3 Data Protection Impact Assessment

Data Protection Impact Assessment - Template

Please refer to the ICO Data Protection Impact Assessment advice at the following link before completing the template below:
<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/data-protection-impact-assessments-dpias/>

Key Contacts	
Project Manager Name & Job Title:	Claire Dempster Senior Officer – Domestic Abuse Strategy & Interventions
Project Manager Email:	Claire.dempster@bedford.gov.uk
Project Manager Phone:	Internal: 49220 DD Tel: 01234 718600
Key Stakeholder Names & Roles:	MARAC Core Agencies listed below
Date:	
Are there any other organisations involved in this project? (Yes / No) If Yes please provide details of the other organisations involved	Yes Bedford Borough Council Children’s Services – Children’s Social Care & Early Help Bedford Borough Council Adult Social Care Bedford Borough Council Housing Bedford Women’s Centre Bedford Hospital – Community Midwife Team Bedford Borough Community Safety Partnership

Appendix 4 MARAC Videos

a) What is MARAC

<https://youtu.be/120kSXCUDic>

b) MARAC Introduction to Risk Identification - DASH

<https://youtu.be/120kSXCUDic>

c) MARAC roles and Information Sharing

<https://youtu.be/AB00K1jiFUc>

d) MARAC meeting action and planning

<https://youtu.be/6pvNKAHQjAk>

Appendix 5 Participant Consent Form, Participant Questionnaire

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1zuMm39oS-Q4LCy_26Uds8d2JCSlleDXR89Z9pZ3MXv-crX4KY2up9D25SUMAi0Sb6PUGkDcr?usp=share_link

Appendix 6 Primary data Coded Groups A-B-C-D

[https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1u24BJaBUxj6cqVsxObVuIQ9pcRYE5aJF?usp=share
link](https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1u24BJaBUxj6cqVsxObVuIQ9pcRYE5aJF?usp=share_link)

Appendix 7 MASH TTE Event Bedfordshire Police

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1fiOwyhSROJ6YE-WoBFo37bwvAB3no0dH/edit?usp=share_link&oid=117703231024162917757&rtpof=true&sd=true

Appendix 8 TTE THRIVE PPT

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1ks5a2-KZyn5_CdvIomdfx_RLMMXjSqw4/edit?usp=share_link&oid=117703231024162917757&rtpof=true&sd=true

Appendix 9 - Ethics Approval

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1xdTUhGd8rfjXjfA1OgPr8LIqphAakESo/view?usp=sharing>

NEXT STEPS

If you have answered ‘No’ to questions 4 to 7, you do not need to take further action.

****Your supervisor will give you BAL TAUGHT/... ethics reference number to insert here and you can continue with your project.**

However, you must submit this section of the form with your dissertation otherwise it will be deemed to be a fail. BAL number: 85

Supervisor signature..... Date

FOR SUPERVISOR’S USE ONLY.

**** Supervisor to enter details of research onto Faculty spreadsheet on Google Drive (<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1j4-uxvgNZO7Y8OsHb5v8ECrAFcQMPkQZoj8a-XcRvIc/edit#gid=0>), using next available reference number, and enter the number in the space below.**

If you have answered ‘Yes’ to any of questions 4 to 7, you will need to complete Section 2 the full Research Ethics Application Form below before you can start your research.

Appendix 10 – Ethics consent E-mail

